

Welcome to the EXA4MIND Newsletter

Who are we? We are a Horizon Europe project that aims to build an extreme data platform that brings together large scale data storage systems and powerful computing infrastructures by implementing novel automated data management and effective data staging.

EXA4MIND at the Czech-Bavarian Supercomputing Summer School 2025

The banner features a photograph of a large, light-colored building with a central tower and a clock tower, set against a blue sky with clouds. The building is surrounded by greenery and a stone well in the foreground. The text is overlaid on a dark blue background on the right side of the image.

**Czech-Bavarian
Supercomputing
Summer School
2025**

9 - 12 September 2025
Panství Dlouhá Lhota - near Prague.

**A session on Supercomputing with Optimised
Data Backends powered by EXA4MIND was
one of the programme's highlights.**

EXA4MIND

QR code

lrz Leibniz-Rechenzentrum
der Bayerischen Akademie der Wissenschaften

VSB TECHNICAL
UNIVERSITY
OF OSTRAVA

IT4INNOVATIONS
NATIONAL SUPERCOMPUTING
CENTER

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The first [Czech-Bavarian Supercomputing Summer School](#) was held during the second week of September at the scenic Dlouhá Lhota estate near Prague, Czech Republic. Students from Germany, Turkey, and the Czech Republic were participating in a dynamic programme featuring **lectures and hands-on sessions** that introduced the basics of modern supercomputing and data-heavy workflows across supercomputers and cloud systems.

The **EXA4MIND** project was a central focus of the event. Presentations by partners from the [Leibniz Supercomputing Centre](#), [IT4Innovations](#), the [Czech Academy of Sciences](#), and [Middle East Technical University](#) highlighted the project's technologies and applications.

Discover more

Events

EXA4MIND at the EuChemS Comp Chem 2025

The 14th European Conference in Computational & Theoretical Chemistry ([EuChemS Comp Chem 2025](#)) was held from 15 to 18 September in Naples, Italy. The conference **gathered leading scientists from academia and industry** to present the latest advancements and explore emerging trends in theoretical and computational chemistry.

Michal Otyepka from [IT4Innovations National Supercomputing Center](#), which is the partner coordinating the EXA4MIND project, attended the conference and together with **Vojtěch Mlýnský**, a researcher from the [Institute of Biophysics of the Czech Academy of Sciences](#) and a member of the EXA4MIND consortium, **presented a poster about EXA4MIND** at the first poster session of the conference on 15 September.

Discover more

EXA4MIND project presented at Researchers' Night

IT4Innovations National Supercomputing Center participated in [Researchers' Night](#), an evening event during which **hundreds of scientific institutions across Europe open their doors** to showcase research and its impact on everyday life.

The EXA4MIND project was represented primarily by David Hurych from [Valeo](#), who delivered a presentation titled "*Artificial Intelligence in System Validation and Beyond*". In addition, [IT4Innovations](#) hosted an **EXA4MIND booth**, where David Hurych screened a demo video illustrating Valeo's application case and he was answering the curious questions of all attendees.

[Discover more](#)

Mark your calendars

Join EXA4MIND at EBDVF 2025

The **European Big Data Value Forum (EBDVF)** 2025 will take place in **Copenhagen from 12 to 14 November**. Organised by the Big Data Value Association (**BDVA**), the EBDVF is the flagship event of the European Big Data Value and Data-Driven AI Research and Innovation community.

EXA4MIND will be there for the third consecutive year, and we are very excited to be back! As part of our sponsorship activities, we will have a stand where we will share the progress and main achievements of the EXA4MIND project to date. As we [did in the 2024 edition](#), we will also host a session with the DataNexus cluster.

[Discover more](#)

List of upcoming events

EXA4MIND is in a pivotal year of its journey, during which the consortium partners are able to showcase tangible results of all the research and development work done during 2023 and 2024. Therefore, **EXA4MIND's presence at national and international events** in 2025 plays an important role in our commitment to open science.

Here is a **list of the upcoming events** in which EXA4MIND will be participating, so you won't miss any of them!

- **SC25**: The International Conference for High Performance Computing, Networking, Storage, and Analysis (SC25) will take place in St. Louis, USA, from 16 to 21 November.
- **SCA/HPCAsia 2026**: The Supercomputing Asia (SCA) and the International Conference on High Performance Computing in Asia-Pacific Region (HPCAsia) will take place in Osaka, Japan, from 26 to 29 January 2026.

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You've received this email because you've shared your contact details with us at ISC High Performance 2025.

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